

Assessment of Physicochemical Parameters and Phytoplankton Composition in Yain'mi Woye Stream, Patigi, Kwara State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the physicochemical parameters and phytoplankton composition in Yain'mi Woye Stream of Kwara State, Nigeria, across four sampling stations: Matokun, Patigi, Tanpafu, and Chekeagi. The following water quality parameters were studied: temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen (DO), total dissolved solids (TDS), turbidity, and biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), and they exhibited significant spatial variations. The highest temperature ($27.10 \pm 0.06^\circ\text{C}$) and turbidity (21.10 ± 0.21 NTU) were observed at Station 1, while Station 2 recorded the highest DO concentration (8.90 ± 0.00 mg/L). Station 3 exhibited the highest BOD level (3.90 ± 0.06 mg/L). No significant differences were detected in phosphate, nitrite, cadmium and copper concentrations across the stations. Phytoplankton identification revealed a total of 162 species spanning 18 genera and 9 taxonomic classes. Chlorophyceae were the most dominant (33.94%), followed by Bacillariophyceae (29.63%), Cyanophyceae (24.69%), and Euglenophyceae (11.73%). Species richness was the highest at Station 1 (28.39%) and lowest at Station 3 (23.46%). *Spirogyra* sp. (12.35%) and *Navicula* sp. (9.88%) were the most abundant individual taxa. The observed spatial differences in both physicochemical parameters and phytoplankton communities suggested varying ecological conditions along the stream. These findings provided a valuable baseline for the level of physicochemical parameters and diversity of phytoplankton in the study area.

Keywords: Ecological assessment, Freshwater ecosystem, Kwara State, Physiochemical Parameter, Phytoplankton diversity, Water quality.

INTRODUCTION

Lotic freshwater bodies are highly dynamic ecosystems that are increasingly vulnerable to anthropogenic disturbances, especially from activities within their catchment areas (Stefanidis and Papastergiadou, 2024). These human-induced influences are commonly referred to as anthropogenic activities. It includes agriculture, industrialization, urban expansion, deforestation and unregulated waste disposal, all of which have been shown to significantly degrade both the quality and quantity of freshwater resources (Dikareva and Simon, 2024; Ali and Rahman, 2025). Such activities alter the natural hydrology and chemical composition of aquatic ecosystems, leading to ecological imbalances and loss of biodiversity (Zolfagharpour *et al.*, 2022).

Among the biological components of aquatic ecosystems, phytoplankton play a pivotal role as one of the primary producers (Wang *et al.*, 2023). They also serve as the foundation of the aquatic food web and are key contributors to primary productivity and carbon cycling (Wang *et al.*, 2023). Their distribution and abundance are influenced by environmental

variables such as light availability, nutrient concentrations and hydrological dynamics (Ali and Rahman, 2025; Mohammed *et al.*, 2024). Importantly, phytoplankton are also recognized as sensitive bioindicators of water quality because their community structure rapidly responds to changes in environmental conditions, including pollution and eutrophication (Awo *et al.*, 2024; Bello, 2024).

Water pollution is caused by the direct or indirect discharge of untreated or inadequately treated effluents that poses a significant threat to the ecological integrity of aquatic systems. Pollutants from domestic sewage, industrial discharges, agricultural runoff and livestock waste introduce toxic substances and excess nutrients into water bodies, leading to conditions that are harmful to aquatic life and unsafe for human use (Pradhan *et al.*, 2022). The effects are far-reaching, negatively impacting individual species, biological communities and even human populations (Keck *et al.*, 2025). It is estimated that more than 14,000 people die daily due to water pollution-related issues (Derrick, 2025).

Monitoring physicochemical characteristics and biological indicators of rivers is essential for understanding their ecological status (Atazadeh, 2023). Some studies have examined the water quality of various freshwater bodies in Nigeria, there remains a lack of comprehensive assessments that integrate both physicochemical and phytoplankton-based indicators, especially in rural or under-monitored watercourses such as the Yain'mi Woye Stream in Kwara State (Abulude *et al.*, 2023). Previous assessments have often focused on either physicochemical parameters or biological indices in isolation, limiting our holistic understanding of ecosystem health (Olomukoro *et al.*, 2022; Adelagun *et al.*, 2022).

Therefore, this study aimed to evaluate the physicochemical parameters and phytoplankton composition of the Yain'mi Woye Stream across four designated stations of Matokun, Patigi, Tanpafu, and Chekeagi.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The study was conducted in March 2025 on the Yain'mi Woye Stream, a tributary of the River Niger, located in Patigi, Kwara State, Nigeria. The stream lies between longitude 5°44'53.5"E and latitude 8°49'25.8"N and flows through several villages in Patigi Local Government Area, including Chekeagi, Matokun, Tanpafu, and Patigi town. These areas are characterised by varying degrees of human activities such as farming, bathing, fishing, and washing.

Sampling Stations

Four sampling stations were selected along the course of the stream based on the ecological setting and human activities. These were designated as Stations 1 to 4:

- **Station 1 (Matokun):** This location is characterised by bathing, washing, and farming activities (Latitude: 8°37'55.3"N; Longitude: 5°46'57.7"E).
- **Station 2 (Patigi):** The station is experiencing regular washing and bathing activities (Latitude: 8°43'30.8"N; Longitude: 5°44'52.2"E).
- **Station 3 (Tanpafu):** Location 3 is primarily dominated by lot of farming activities during the rainy season and dry season (Latitude: 8°39'46.5"N; Longitude: 5°45'43.6"E).
- **Station 4 (Chekeagi):** This location is at the stream source, with minimal human activities, fishing the common activity observed (Latitude: 8°42'24.0"N; Longitude: 5°44'30.8"E).

Water Sample Collection

Water samples were collected in one-litre capacity plastic bottles at the hypolimnion layer early in the morning from each station. Temperature and transparency were measured on-site using a Hanna Combo pH meter and a Secchi disc, respectively. The collected samples were transported to Biofare Analytical Consultants Laboratory, Ilorin, Kwara State, for physico-chemical analysis. Analytical procedures followed the Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater (APHA, AWWA, & WEF, 2022).

Phytoplankton Collection and Analysis

Phytoplankton samples were collected using a standard surface plankton net with a 25 cm diameter stainless steel ring and a conical nylon mesh. A 50 cl glass collection jar was attached to the net and secured with cotton rope (Salisu *et al.*, 2024). The net was trawled back and forth through the water to collect samples. Each sample was immediately transferred into a 1-litre plastic container containing 4% buffered formalin as preservative and transported to the laboratory.

In the laboratory, samples were allowed to settle for 24 hours, and the supernatant was carefully decanted to concentrate the plankton. The concentrated sample was thoroughly mixed, and 1 mL was drawn using a pipette and placed on a glass slide. Microscopic examination was carried out using an Olympus binocular microscope at 100× and 400× magnifications (Majumdar and Avishek, 2024). Enumeration was conducted using the natural unit method and reported as units or organisms per millilitre (mL) according to Adama *et al.* (2023). Phytoplankton diversity was evaluated using the Evaluation of Phytoplankton Diversity

Statistical Analysis

One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to assess significant differences among the physico-chemical parameters across sampling stations, with significance set at $p < 0.05$. Community structure and diversity of phytoplankton were evaluated using Simpson's Diversity Index (SDI), Margalef's Index (D), Shannon-Wiener Index (H'), and Evenness (E) (Anyanwu *et al.*, 2021).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Physicochemical Parameters of Yain'mi Woye Stream

The physicochemical characteristics of Yain'mi Woye Stream across the four sampling stations are presented in Table 1. The data revealed spatial variations in water quality parameters, which were attributed to

both natural factors and human activities along the stream.

Temperature showed significant variation ($P \leq 0.05$) among stations, with the highest recorded at Station 1 ($27.10 \pm 0.06^\circ\text{C}$), potentially due to open canopy and human activities like washing and bathing (Akhtar *et al.*, 2020). The lowest temperature was observed at Station 2 ($25.73 \pm 0.04^\circ\text{C}$), possibly influenced by groundwater inflows or shaded areas. Temperature directly affects phytoplankton productivity, solubility of gases, and aquatic metabolism (Pandit *et al.*, 2020). pH ranged from slightly neutral to alkaline, with the highest value at Station 4 (8.43 ± 0.03), likely due to bicarbonate buffering or high photosynthetic activity (Heino *et al.*, 2021). Slightly alkaline conditions support phytoplankton growth (Lehner *et al.*, 2022), and the recorded range (7.67–8.43) was within WHO-recommended limits for aquatic life.

Dissolved Oxygen (DO) was highest at Station 2 (8.90 ± 0.00 mg/L), suggesting good aeration and low organic pollution. The lowest DO value was observed at Station 3 (5.87 ± 0.03 mg/L), potentially due to increased bacterial decomposition or organic loading, reflecting pollution vulnerability from nearby human activities (Hassan and El Nemr, 2020; Akhtar *et al.*, 2021).

Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) and Conductivity were highest at Station 3 (141.97 ± 0.09 mg/L and 170.57 ± 0.38 $\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$, respectively), likely resulting

from agricultural runoff or domestic wastewater. Station 1 recorded the lowest TDS (135.50 ± 0.29 mg/L), indicating relatively clear water. Elevated conductivity reflects higher mineral or ionic concentrations (Akachukwu *et al.*, 2023).

Turbidity peaked at Station 1 (21.10 ± 0.21 NTU), suggesting significant suspended solids, possibly from erosion or anthropogenic disturbance (Abdullahi *et al.*, 2022). High turbidity can limit light penetration and affect aquatic photosynthesis. Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD) was highest at Station 3 (3.90 ± 0.06 mg/L), indicating high organic pollution and microbial activity. The lowest BOD was at Station 2 (2.20 ± 0.12 mg/L), supporting its status as the least polluted (Akachukwu *et al.*, 2023).

Nutrient levels were mostly stable across the stations. Phosphate and Nitrite showed no significant differences. However, Nitrate was significantly higher at Stations 1 and 2 (3.46 ± 0.01 mg/L), potentially from agricultural or faecal sources (Hill, 2023). Moderate nutrient levels may support phytoplankton growth, though excessive enrichment risks eutrophication (Abdullahi *et al.*, 2022).

Heavy metals analysis revealed high Iron levels at Stations 1 and 4 (0.20 ± 0.01 mg/L), possibly due to leaching from soil or anthropogenic inputs. Cadmium and Copper levels showed no significant differences between stations, but remain concerning due to potential bioaccumulation (Hussain *et al.*, 2022).

Table 1: Level of Physicochemical parameters at stations in Yain'mi Woye Stream In Patigi, Kwara State

Parameter	Station 1	Station 2	Station 3	Station 4
Temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)	27.10 ± 0.06^a	25.73 ± 0.04^c	26.37 ± 0.20^b	$26.17 \pm 0.22^{b/c}$
pH	7.70 ± 0.06^c	7.67 ± 0.03^c	8.17 ± 0.03^b	8.43 ± 0.03^a
Dissolved Oxygen (mg/l)	6.31 ± 0.01^b	8.90 ± 0.00^a	5.87 ± 0.03^c	6.23 ± 0.03^b
Conductivity ($\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$)	137.57 ± 0.03^b	134.80 ± 0.00^c	170.57 ± 0.38^a	132.10 ± 0.21^d
TDS (mg/l)	135.50 ± 0.29^d	139.97 ± 0.32^b	141.97 ± 0.09^a	136.47 ± 0.09^c
Turbidity (NTU)	21.10 ± 0.21^a	18.03 ± 0.26^c	19.30 ± 0.12^b	16.43 ± 0.09^d
BOD (mg/l)	2.63 ± 0.09^b	2.20 ± 0.12^c	3.90 ± 0.06^a	2.77 ± 0.03^b
Phosphate (PO_4^{3-})	0.13 ± 0.00^a	0.15 ± 0.00^a	0.14 ± 0.00^a	0.20 ± 0.06^a
Nitrite (NO_2^-)	0.14 ± 0.01^a	0.16 ± 0.01^a	0.13 ± 0.00^a	0.20 ± 0.06^a
Nitrate (NO_3^-)	3.46 ± 0.01^a	3.42 ± 0.01^a	2.94 ± 0.03^b	3.00 ± 0.05^b
Iron (Pb)	0.20 ± 0.01^a	0.14 ± 0.02^b	0.10 ± 0.01^b	0.03 ± 0.01^a
Cadmium (Cd)	0.07 ± 0.06^a	0.00 ± 0.00^a	0.00 ± 0.00^a	0.07 ± 0.03^a
Copper (Cu)	0.32 ± 0.00^a	0.30 ± 0.00^a	0.32 ± 0.04^a	0.43 ± 0.09^a

Mean values of each Parameter across different Sampling Stations

Phytoplankton Composition and Distribution

A total of 167 phytoplankton individuals across 18 genera and 9 classes were identified (Table 2). The Chlorophyceae group was the most dominant (33.94%), followed by Bacillariophyceae (29.63%), Cyanophyceae (24.69%), and Euglenophyceae

(11.73%). Station 1 had the highest species composition (28.39%), while Station 3 recorded the lowest (23.46%). The most dominant species were *Spirogyra sp.* (12.35%) under Chlorophyceae, followed by *Navicula sp.* (9.88%) and *Nitzschia sp.* (9.26%) under Bacillariophyceae, and *Microcystis sp.*

(9.26%) under Cyanophyceae. Rare species included *Diatoma sp.* and *Euglena viridis* (0.62% each). The variation in species composition across stations may be due to difference in water chemistry, nutrient availability and human disturbances. Stations near settlements with washing and bathing activities may favor resilient taxa like *Microcystis sp.* and *Oscillatoria sp.*, known to serve as indicators of pollution (Akachukwu *et al.*, 2023). The phytoplankton composition suggests a moderately

impacted aquatic system capable of supporting diverse algal communities.

Nutrient input from agricultural runoff and organic waste likely enhances the growth of Chlorophyta and Bacillariophyta, as observed in similar studies (Ray *et al.*, 2023; Maneesh and Siva, 2022). These groups are often used as bioindicators due to their sensitivity to environmental fluctuations and pollutants.

Table 2: Phytoplankton Composition and Distribution in Yainmi Woye Stream, Patigi, Kwara State.

GROUP	SPECIES	Station One	Station Two	Station Three	Station Four	Total	RA (%)	
Chlorophyta	<i>Spirogyra grevilleana</i>	6	4	5	5	20	12.35	
	<i>Chara braunil</i>	0	0	0	2	2	1.23	
	<i>Chlamydomonas reinhardtii</i>	2	3	1	0	6	3.7	
	<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	2	1	2	1	6	3.7	
	<i>Pediastrum boryanum</i>	4	2	1	3	10	6.17	
	<i>Nitella opaca</i>	3	2	1	1	7	4.32	
	<i>Cladophera glomerata</i>	1	1	2	0	4	2.47	
	Cyanophyta	<i>Microcystis viridis</i>	4	3	5	3	15	9.26
<i>Nostoc sphaeroides</i>		1	1	1	1	4	2.47	
<i>Anabaeba planktonica</i>		1	4	2	4	11	6.79	
<i>Oscillatoria limosa</i>		3	2	3	2	10	6.17	
Bacillariophyta	<i>Fragilaria crotonensis</i>	3	0	1	0	4	2.47	
	<i>Navicula crytocephala</i>	3	5	4	4	16	9.88	
	<i>Nitzschia palea</i>	4	3	3	5	15	9.26	
	<i>Gomphonema gracile</i>	1	1	0	0	2	1.23	
	<i>Cyclotella atomus</i>	2	3	2	3	10	6.17	
	<i>Achnanthydium minutissimum</i>	0	1	0	0	1	0.62	
	Euglenophyta	<i>Euglena acus</i>	3	2	4	3	12	7.42
		<i>Euglena viridis</i>	1	0	0	0	1	0.62
<i>Phacuspleuronecres</i>		2	1	1	2	6	3.7	
Total	46 (28.39%)	39 (24.07%)	38 (23.46%)	39 (24.08%)	162	100%		

Table 3: Phytoplankton Species Diversity Indices in Yainmi Woye Stream, 2025

Station	1	2	3	4
Taxa S	18	17	16	14
Individuals	46	39	38	39
Simpson_1-D	0.949	0.949	0.940	0.937
Shannon_H	2.752	2.013	2.604	2.543
Species Evenness	0.952	0.711	0.939	0.964
Margalef	4.439	4.367	4.123	3.548

Phytoplankton species diversity indices revealed noticeable variations among stations (Table 3). Species richness was highest at Station 1 (18 taxa), followed by Station 2 (17), Station 3 (16), and Station 4 (14). Simpson's Index (1-D) values ranged from 0.949 at Stations 1 and 2 to 0.937 at Station 4, indicating a fairly even species distribution. The Shannon-Weiner Index was highest at Station 1 (2.752), suggesting the most diverse phytoplankton community, while Station 2 had the lowest value (2.013), implying lower evenness and diversity. Species Evenness was peaked at Station 4 (0.964) and was lowest at Station 2 (0.711), indicating a more balanced distribution of species in Station 4 (Chugani, 2025). Margalef's Index, reflecting richness, was highest at Station 1 (4.439) and lowest at Station 4 (3.548). This shows that Station 1 was the most ecologically rich (Kitikidou *et al.*, 2024).

CONCLUSION

This study provides a comprehensive overview of the spatial variations in physicochemical parameters and phytoplankton communities along Yain'mi Woye Stream. The results show distinct differences among the four sampling stations, reflecting natural variations in environmental conditions across the stream. The diverse phytoplankton assemblage, dominated by Chlorophyceae, Bacillariophyceae, and Cyanophyceae, highlights the ecological complexity of the system. The baseline information generated on water quality characteristics and phytoplankton diversity serves as a useful reference for future ecological assessments, long-term monitoring, and comparative studies within the region.

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